

COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF INVESTMENT ATTRACTIVENESS OF REGIONS

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Annotation

The level of economic development of the region is largely determined by investment activity. Attracting investment in the regional economy requires increasing investment attractiveness, constant monitoring of its state for effective management.

Key words: Investments, investment attractiveness, rating, comparative assessment, regional economy, expert assessment.

In order to analyze the effectiveness of investment policy implementation and to develop recommendations for its improvement, it is proposed to conduct a comprehensive comparative assessment of investment attractiveness of regions. The most common method of such assessments is the method of ranking regions. As a result, a ranking of regions is compiled.

The rating method is based on the idea of determining the rating score and ranking the region based on the level of socio-economic development and political potential. It is by this method that the region's place in socio-economic development is determined. From this point of view, the rating indicator of a region acts as a mechanism of incentives for development [1].

With the emergence of relevant and rapidly updated statistical information on various aspects of territorial development, ratings have become widely used for comparative assessment of living standards and analysis of the dynamics of various economic, social, political and environmental processes in the regions.

The study of modern domestic and foreign methods of assessing the investment attractiveness of the regional economy shows their great diversity. These methods can be divided into two main groups.

The first group consists of methods based largely on expert surveys to obtain initial information for analysis. They include methods of rating assessment of

the world's leading economic journals, assessments of world and domestic rating agencies and some others. The advantages of the methods of the first group are:

- consideration of the characteristics that are really important to the investor;
- sufficiently high efficiency;
- integrated use of statistical data and expert assessments. However, the

methods of this group have disadvantages:

- generality of the assessment of investment attractiveness of the region's economy, which reduces their practical applicability when choosing a specific recipient region;

- the presence of an element of subjectivity;
- weak correlation with the level of innovation activity.

The second group of techniques is based on the use of statistical information as a basis. The main advantage of these techniques is their focus on the calculation of a comprehensive indicator, which allows us to accurately determine the degree of investment attractiveness of the region's economy, which makes them more practical to use. Moreover, they are based on obtaining initial information only on objective components of investment attractiveness, which, in our opinion, allows us to obtain more accurate results.

The disadvantages of these methodologies include: insufficient validity of the system of indicators for assessing the investment attractiveness of the regional economy and some incompleteness, since the developers usually do not take into account the strategic objectives of the statistical assessment of investment attractiveness, which determines the whole process of its implementation, and are usually limited to the clustering of regions by the level of investment attractiveness of their economies. Nevertheless, in our opinion, an important element of the assessment should be the analysis of the dynamics of changes in the investment attractiveness of regional economies for investment as a comprehensive indicator and obtaining forecast estimates with their subsequent classification.

Creating a methodology for any rating involves the following steps:

1. Creating a system of indicators.
2. Identifying sources of information.
3. Selecting a method for aggregating data into a comprehensive rating.

The system of indicators is usually formed based on the objectives of the study. At this stage, it is advisable to categorize indicators according to different criteria to properly form a comprehensive rating. Indicators are divided into

stimulators, destimulators and neutral indicators depending on their orientation. Stimulators are indicators, the increase of which is assessed positively and indicates the development of the region, improvement of the social, economic or environmental situation (for example, the level of employment, the volume of investment in fixed capital). Destimulators are indicators, the decrease of which positively characterizes socio-economic phenomena and processes in the region (e.g., emissions of pollutants into the atmosphere, unemployment rate).

Neutral indicators serve as additional, clarifying information, and the distribution of regions by their value is often used to form homogeneous groups of objects under study (e.g., population of the territory, total land area) [2].

The complex indicator is determined by summing up the numerical values of individual indicators of investment attractiveness.

The number of private factors includes various social, economic, environmental characteristics of the regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, for example, the volume of industrial production, employment rate, crime rate, etc. The need to take into account such characteristics is explained by their extreme importance for investors.

Integral indicators of investment attractiveness of regions are relative coefficients, which, therefore, are not related to the size of the territory or population of the region. All individual characteristics of investment attractiveness are taken into account when calculating integral (composite) values measured in relative units - per capita, in rates, in fractions.

The comprehensive comparative assessment of the region's investment attractiveness should meet the requirements of comprehensiveness and systematicity, ensure comparability in time and space of the obtained levels of assessment, allow to study the impact of factors, conduct economic interpretation of the obtained results and the formation of meaningful conclusions from them. In addition, it should effectively carry out the statistical assessment of the region's investment attractiveness in modern conditions.

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